

STUDY OF RESISTIVE AND RESONANT AMPLIFIERS USING VIRTUAL DEVICES (STANDS)

O.O.Zaripov, F.F.Isaev, S.J.Nimatov, S.M.Zaripov
 Tashkent state technical university
doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11179340

Abstract. Amplifiers are widely used in the field of electrical engineering and are designed to increase the power of signals. Such devices are designed to amplify electrical signals in the national economy in a wide range of frequencies, including the audible sound range.

Physical or mathematical modeling methods are used in the development of any device in the study of natural sciences.

Physical modeling requires large financial resources, often physical modeling cannot be implemented due to the complexity of the devices. For example, considerable difficulties are encountered when modeling large integrated circuits. In such cases, mathematical or schematic engineering modeling methods are used [1].

Another type of amplifiers - resonant amplifiers - is widely used in electronics, radio and electrical engineering, automation. These types of amplifiers are in high demand. Transmission and amplification of the desired signal without interference is of great importance.

Resistive amplifiers use resistors as a load. Since inductance coils are not used in these amplifiers (we do not take into account the inductance in the legs of the elements), there are no oscillation processes in them. Resistors act as internal and external loads in resistive amplifiers. Figure 1 shows the most commonly used single-stage resistive amplifier circuit, assembled with a common-emitter circuit. All other conditions being equal, this circuit has the largest power gain. . Internal and external loads are carried out by R_k and R_n resistors, respectively.

Picture 1. The principle scheme of the resistive amplifier.

An external load can be used as a load instead of a resistor, an amplifier (speaker), a relay, a communication line, etc. can be connected.

In harmonic signals and amplifiers with a narrow effective spectrum, it is not desirable to use aperiodic amplifiers with a frequency band from constant current (zero frequency) to high frequencies, because in these cases it is difficult to have a sufficiently large amplification (especially at tens of megahertz frequencies).

2- picture The principle scheme of the resonance amplifier.

In addition, the inherent noise of amplifiers is amplified, because the power of these noises is directly proportional to the bandwidth. For this reason, resonant LC-loop amplifiers are used to amplify narrowband signals.

2 - the picture shows the circuit assembled on the basis of the "Electronics Workbench" program. The inductance Lk results from the condition of resonance in the oscillation circuit Lk, Ck (resonance is observed when the frequency of the input signal is equal to the resonance frequency of the oscillation circuit, and this resonance frequency is determined by the following formula:

$$f_{rez} = 1/2\pi$$

Using the Analysis / AC Frequency command, the amplitude-frequency and phase-frequency characteristics (AChX and FChX) of the resonant amplifier are obtained.

Picture 1. Amplifier AChX and FChX

It is determined that the resonance frequency corresponds to the frequency of the input signal.

Figure 3. Shows the output AChX and FChX oscillograms. When taking AChX, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that it is not desirable to have a very sharp maximum point, at this time it will be difficult to determine the resonance frequency. It is desirable to make the AChX characteristic "more common".

To carry out this study, it is necessary to apply frequency signals located in and out of the band to the input of the amplifier. On the oscilloscope, the gain is determined for each frequency. These results are compared with those obtained with AChX. Conclusions are given.

Schematic modeling of radio electronic devices "Electronic Workbench" program is designed for creation and analysis of electronic circuits. In mastering the sciences of physics, electronics, electrical engineering, it is appropriate to study the virtual circuits collected in this program along with real stands [1-2].

In conclusion, the article covers the results of the research of resistive and resonant amplifiers using virtual stands. Information about amplifiers and their types is given.

Resonance amplifiers, their types, characteristics, methods of their creation are given. Resonant and resistive amplifiers were modeled and studied in the "Electronics Workbench" (EWB) program. Research results are presented in the form of amplitude-frequency characteristics and phase-frequency characteristics oscillograms.

References

1. Дорошков А.В. Теория и практика виртуальных исследований устройств электроники: Учеб. пособие. – СПб: НИУ ИТМО; ИХиБТ, 2013
2. Амелина М.А., Амелин С.А. Программа схемотехнического моделирования Micro-Cap. Версии 9, 10. – Смоленск, Смоленский филиал НИУ МЭИ, 2013.